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Research Article

**DIAGNOSTIC PRECISION OF TRANSVAGINAL SONOGRAPHY
FOR OVARIAN ENDOMETRIOMA**¹Muhammad Irfan Zulfiqar, ²Umer Naqash, ³Saba Ishtiaq¹DHQ Hospital Nankana Sahib, ²THQ Hospital Sarai Alamgir Gujrat, ³Fatima Memorial Hospital College of Medicine and Dentistry.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Aim: To regulate the diagnostic performance of specific ultrasound features to distinguish endometriomas from other adnexal masses.

Study design: A retrospective study.

Place and Duration: In the Obstetrics & Gynecology Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2018 to March 2019.

Methods: The study was held among 65 patients who attended the Infertility Center. Infertile women > 25 years old, patients undergoing laparotomy or laparoscopy were included in the study. Patients with ectopic pregnancy and pelvic inflammatory disease were excluded. All patients were prospectively evaluated by vaginal examination. Ultrasound criteria for diagnosing

endometrioma are round shape, low-level diffuse internal echoes, cystic structure in the adnexa, multilocularity, hyperechoic focal walls and wall thickness.

Results: Histopathological findings of adnexal mass are endometrioma in forty cases, dermoid cyst (n = 3), malignant tumor (n = 2), hemorrhagic cyst (n = 6) and benign cyst. Benign torsional cysts of the ovaries n = 1, broad ligament hematoma n = 1, paraplegic cyst n = 1, hydrosalpinx n = 1 and a single functional cyst n = 7, the results were statistically analyzed and sensitivity determined. specificity of TVS with diagnosed endometrioma was 90%, sensitivity was 86%; 91% was PPV and 98% negative predictive value.

Conclusion: Adnexal mass with low diffuse internal echoes and no specific tumor features is highly advanced in the case of endometriomas if there are multilocularity/hyper echoic wall foci present.

Keywords: TVS, endometrioma, adnexal mass.

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INTRODUCTION:

Endometriosis is the presence of functional endometrial epithelium and stroma in an ectopic position outside the uterus. Endometrioma has a prevalence of 24% among all ovarian cysts. It weakens due to accompanying pain and infertility. It has an ultrasonic appearance, from anechoic to echogenic cysts, from masses containing solid tissue and many septations.

Laparoscopy is a standard gold endometriosis study evaluating abdominal and pelvic implants, but it can also be used as the primary imaging method in the initial assessment of suspected gynecological pathology. Ultrasound is also useful for displaying an internal echo scattered at a low level or possibly a level of liquid or fluid waste or mass containing a clear appearance with compartments and solid tissues.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

A retrospective study was conducted in the Obstetrics & Gynecology Unit II of Services Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from March 2018 to March 2019 and the results were statistically evaluated. Patients with endometrioma older than 25 years, infertile,

patients undergoing laparotomy or laparoscopy for endometrioma were selected and excluding women with PID and ectopic pregnancy.

All patients underwent preoperative transvaginal examination. In the diagnosis of endometrioma, various ultrasound features were observed, including cystic appearance, intentional low-level echoes, wall thickness, multilocularity and nodulatory. All patients underwent laparoscopy or laparotomy. Next, the ultrasound diagnostic features were compared with the histopathological report. All ultrasound features were statistically correct in terms of diagnosis, severity, specificity, probability coefficient and probability coefficient.

RESULTS:

Endometrioma was confirmed in forty patients out of sixty-five on histopathology, hemorrhagic cyst (n = 3), severe cystic malignancy (n = 2). N = 11 patients had mild problems such as functional cyst (n = 7), hemorrhagic cyst of ovarian torsion (n = 1), broad ligament hematoma (n = 1), hydrosalpinx (n = 1) and paratubal cyst. (n = 1).

Table I: Histopathological findings of adnexal mass

Histopathological Findings	=n
Dermoid Cyst	3
Endometrioma	40
Malignancy	2
Hemorrhagic Cyst	6
Ovarian Torsion	1
Benign Cyst	11
Paratubal Cyst	1
Broad Ligament Hematoma	1
Cyst Simple	7
Hydrosalpinx	1

Sensitivity of the vaginal examination in the diagnosis of endometrioma was 86%, specificity 90%, estimated 91%, and negative 98%. The diagnostic value of each ultrasound was assessed separately. Comparing histopathological reports and preoperative ultrasound results. It was found that the most accurate ultrasound features for diagnosing endometrioma with 99% accuracy are low-level internal echoes without wall tuberosity with a 0.6 probability coefficient and a 48-

probability coefficient. After omnipotence, accuracy was reduced to 91%: 0.4 probability coefficient + 17, sensitivity 65% and 96%. Similarly, 93% sensitivity, 83% specificity + probability ratio 0.1+ probability of endometrioma recognition by internal echoes. indicator 5 was 84% normal for diagnosis. The wall thickness was also carefully observed. The thick wall accuracy was 54%, specificity 52%, sensitivity 65%, probability factor 1, and probability factor 0.7. While

the accuracy of the thin wall appearance is 55%, the specificity is 56%, the 48% probability is 0.9, and the positive probability is 1. The ultrasound characteristic of the cystic appearance is only 95%, the specificity

19% + the probability coefficient is 1, - the probability coefficient is 0.3, the accuracy is reduced to 31% among other cysts.

Figure I: Maximum characteristic curve of the receiver operation for diagnosing endometrioma using an ultrasonic function

It shows the relationship between specificity and sensitivity. Based on several ultrasound features that confirm transvaginal examination as a diagnostic tool for endometriosis, the recipient of endometrioma diagnosis has a higher operational reason than the recipient.

Table II: Diagnostic efficacy of ultrasound characteristics in discriminating between endometrioma and uterine insensitivity

US. F.	Endom n=40	De r. n=3	H.Cy st n=6	B.C yst N=11	Mali g n=2	Sen . %	Sp. %	Ac cu r %	=-ve L. Rati o	+ve L. Rati o
Cyst + thick wall	19	0	4	4	1	48	56	55	0.9	1
Cystic Features	38	3	6	11	2	95	19	31	0.3	1
Cyst. + int. echoe	37	0	5	3	2	93	83	84	0.1	5
Cyst + thick wall	25	0	0	6	1	63	52	54	0.7	1
L.L.E. no neo+ no fib	26	0	2	0	0	65	96	91	0.4	17
L.L.E. Echoe	38	0	3	3	0	95	81	83	0.1	5
L.L.E. no leo., wall foci or multilocularity	18	0	0	0	0	45	99	99	0.6	48
L.L.E. # leo., & multilocularity	12	0	0	0	0	30	100	88	0.7	64
L.L.E., no neo, nowall foci	12	0	0	0	0	30	99	88	0.7	32

DISCUSSION:

Ultrasound is essentially the first study required in patients with clinical symptoms that may suggest pelvic disease. There is a range that experts describe as classic endometrioma. Proper reporting and recording of specific ultrasound features help to distinguish several appendicular masses, and also serves as important guidelines for patient management. Several studies have combined the use of transvaginal testing not only with CA 125 plasma levels, but also with other tumor markers in the serum to achieve diagnostic accuracy and to distinguish

endometrioma from other ovarian tumors. Similarly, the characteristic Doppler blood flow model differentiates endometriomas of malignant ovarian tumors. The results of our study show that the sensitivity of the vaginal examination in the diagnosis of endometrioma is 86%, 90% specificity, 91% positive predictive value and 98% negative predictive value. Volpi et al showed that endometrioma sensitivity was 82%, specificity was 97% and predictive value was 94%, respectively, with the same transvaginal test capability.

Figure 1: Endometrioma in a 28-year-old woman radiates internal echoes of low and intermittent peripheral echogenic foci. Fig. 2: Detailed view of endometrioma, hyperechoic wall foci (arrow) and low-level echoes in a 33-year-old woman. Figure 3: 40-year-old female patient with multicellular endometrioma, internal septum (arrow), adnexa cyst with low echo.

Figure 4: Endometrioma R Ovary, low level diffuse echoes and tubular focal wall tuberosity in a 42-year-old woman. Figure 5: L-ovary, low level echoes and tubular focal wall tuberosity in a 29-year-old woman (arrow). Fig. 6: R Ovarian Cystic teratoma in a 32-year-old woman, regional arrow with light echoes in the shadow and low internal diffuse echoes.

The presence of low-level echoes is a homogeneous diagnosis for many studies where the wall thickness as well as the contour, shape and position differ between tests. It is important to understand how any feature or set of features increases or decreases the likelihood ratio in the diagnosis of endometrioma, because it is important to direct the assessment of information to identify features of the highest importance and effort

and confusion. to characterize functions that are not relevant. Alcazar et al found that 55 masses attached to 27 endometriomas "were separated from the other 55 masses using a round homogeneous hypoechoic low-level echo mass, with a positive probability of 9 and a positive probability of 0.1". The same results can be compared with our study, because cystic results

with low-level echoes are 84% accuracy + probability factor 5 and - probability factor 0.1.

Although 95% of endometriomas have a low internal echo, they only show a cystic feature in the USA. This did not improve diagnostic performance. Hyperechoic wall foci showed a positive probability of 6.2. Many studies show that a hemorrhagic cyst has low-level echoes that help us make a final diagnosis with a sensitivity of 55% and a specificity of 48%, which helps us to make a final diagnosis that conflicts with our study. Specificity 56% + probability coefficient 1. In our LLE study, multifocal, focused but wall less thin walls can easily be compared with tests carried out with 99% accuracy, 99% specificity, 45% sensitivity, - a probability factor of 0.6 and a probability factor of 48.

CONCLUSION:

Adnexal mass, which does not have diffuse low-level internal echoes and specific tumor characteristics, is a very good recommendation for endometrioma if multilayer foci or hyper wall echo are present. A patient with low diffuse mass and other ultrasound features can take advantage of additional photos.

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